

1 Fulvic Acid Modulates Mucosal Immunity in
2 Fish Skin: Sustainable Aquaculture Solution
3 or Environmental Risk Factor?

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18

19 Abstract

20 This is the first study determining the effects of bath exposure to fulvic acid, a humic substance,
21 on the skin mucosal immunity of rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*). Humic substances have
22 recently been gaining attention for their increasing concentrations in aquatic ecosystems and
23 their use as supplements in sustainable aquaculture. This study demonstrated that water
24 exposure to fulvic acid at concentrations of 5 mg C/L and 50 mg C/L increased lysozyme and
25 alkaline phosphatase activities in the mucus by approximately 2-fold and 2.5 to 3.2-fold,
26 respectively. Furthermore, exposure to 50 mg C/L resulted in a 77.0 % increase in mucosal
27 immunoglobulin concentrations compared to the other groups. Importantly, all mucus samples
28 demonstrated significant antibacterial activity against *Yersinia ruckeri*, with control mucus
29 reducing bacterial growth by 44.5 % and exposure to fulvic acid increasing this effect to 26.3 %.
30 Although these modulations show promise for application in aquaculture, alterations of the
31 beneficial microbiota from long-term exposure in natural waters can be expected. Monitoring the
32 rising concentrations of humic substances in natural water bodies is therefore urgently needed.
33 Overall, this study represents the first investigation revealing the ability of humic substances to
34 modulate skin mucosal immunity and the capacity to combat microorganisms.

35

36 Graphical Abstract:

37

38 **1 Statement of Environmental Implication**

39 Concentrations of humic substances are significantly increasing in freshwater bodies. Although
40 these naturally occurring substances may not seem highly hazardous at first glance, the sudden
41 increases could pose unknown risks to aquatic life. This study is the first to evaluate the effects of
42 fulvic acid (FA) on the skin mucosal immunity of rainbow trout. Exposure to FA increased several
43 aspects of mucosal immunity but could impact beneficial microbiota. This research highlights the
44 dual nature of FA, holding promise for sustainable aquaculture while posing an environmental
45 threat. It underscores the need for strict monitoring, providing valuable insight into both research
46 fields.

47 **2 Highlights**

- 48 • Concentrations of humic substances in natural waters are increasing recently

- 49 • Unmonitored humic substances pose a risk to fish in aquaculture and the environment
- 50 • Fulvic acid increased innate immune response in the skin mucus of rainbow trout
- 51 • Lysozyme, alkaline phosphatase, and immunoglobulin content increased after exposure
- 52 • Increased antibacterial defenses protect against pathogens, but may alter microbiota

53 3 Introduction

54 Natural organic matter (NOM) is a ubiquitous component in ecosystems, resulting from the
55 degradation of organic materials, mainly from plants. In aquatic environments, up to 95 % of the
56 dissolved organic matter (DOC) are humic substances (HSs) [1, 2]. The concentrations of DOC
57 found in aquatic ecosystems can vary significantly, but organisms have evolved alongside these
58 natural xenobiotics and have adapted to their presence [3]. Analyzing data from 7,514 lakes from
59 6 continents, Sobek et al. [4] reported concentrations between 0.1 and 335 mg DOC/L, although
60 most lakes (87 %) had DOC concentrations between 1 and 20 mg C/L. Noteworthy is that the study
61 used data collected between 1984 and 2005, and over the past few decades, natural lakes and
62 rivers have experienced a significant increase in DOC levels. From 1986 to 2015, the DOC profiles
63 in high-elevation lakes in the northeastern US have shifted from low-DOC (< 5 mg/L) to moderate
64 DOC lakes (5-30 mg/L) [5]. According to the United Kingdom Upland Waters Monitoring Network
65 [6], the median DOC concentration in some lakes increased by over 280 % between 1989 and
66 2021 (Supplement Table 1). In 47.6 % of all freshwaters monitored, the median DOC
67 concentration increased by at least 2-fold and 9.5 % by over 3-fold. Seasonal variation can even
68 exceed tenfold [7-10]. Such significant and rapid changes in the aquatic environment can have
69 severe consequences for the organisms that inhabit it. Negative effects of increased DOC
70 concentrations on invertebrates have been studied using both model organisms, as well as
71 freshwater amphipods and brachiopods, and demonstrated reduced offspring numbers and
72 increased oxidative stress and damage [11-13]. Nevertheless, information about the effects of
73 increased DOC concentrations on vertebrates, especially fish, is limited.

74 Recently, HSs received significant attention as potential supplements for fish in aquaculture
75 through both feed and water addition [14-16]. Intriguingly, these studies often report stimulation
76 of various components of the fish immune system. Louvado et al. [17] reported a beneficial

77 modulation of the skin microbiome of juvenile European sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) after 28
78 days of exposure to 2.5 mg/L of a HS (an estimated DOC concentration of ~ 1.25 mg C/L, based
79 on an average carbon content of HSs of around 50 %). Unfortunately, most aquaculture studies
80 only analyze beneficial effects, often using low concentrations. This approach results in limited
81 information for any risk assessment. Recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS) are designed to
82 operate on low water discharge, which can cause the accumulation of dissolved organic matter,
83 particularly FA, over time, even without additional supplementation [18]. This accumulation can
84 result in unexpected increases in FA concentrations in the water, with unknown consequences
85 for the fish. Our previous research demonstrated that FA, which was initially beneficial to fish
86 larvae at low to moderate concentrations, became detrimental at higher levels, causing edemas,
87 hematomas, and increased mortality [19]. Although there is growing interest in using HSs for
88 aquaculture, understanding their effects on fish immune responses is primarily limited to
89 systemic reactions and remains overall limited.

90 Fish are in much closer contact and exchange with their environment than terrestrial animals,
91 which results in continuous exposure to various microorganisms, both pathogenic and
92 nonpathogenic. Intensive aquaculture settings facilitate disease transmission, which can result in
93 high mortality rates and significant economic losses [20-22]. Similarly, wastewater from
94 agricultural and industrial sources can increase levels of microorganisms in natural water bodies,
95 which can pose additional challenges to wild fish populations [23, 24]. Surfaces of fish exposed
96 directly to the environment are particularly susceptible to colonization and invasion by
97 commensal and pathogenic microorganisms. Therefore, the mucosal barrier plays a crucial role
98 in fish defense.

99 Goblet cells and other specialized cells secrete mucus, a primary defense mechanism. The mucus
100 forms the first line of defense by continuously trapping and removing invading pathogens before
101 they can reach the underlying epithelial cells [25-28]. The mucus is primarily composed of mucins,
102 which are large and highly glycosylated proteins [29]. These proteins determine the viscoelastic
103 and adhesive properties of the mucosal layer. Additionally, the mucus contains various innate and
104 adaptive immune molecules that function as antibacterial and antimicrobial factors, including
105 immunoglobulins, lysozymes, and phosphatases [28, 30, 31]. These factors are crucial in

106 recognizing, labeling, degrading, and neutralizing external pathogens and pathobionts. This helps
107 control the microorganismal load and exhibits anti-inflammatory activities linked to wound-
108 healing processes [28, 32, 33]. Interaction with pathogens activates the antimicrobial activity of
109 mucosal defense parameters, emphasizing the importance of mucosal immunity in defending
110 against pathogens [34, 35].

111 Previous research has demonstrated that the application of FA baths can stimulate the systemic
112 immune response of juvenile rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) and zebrafish larvae (*Danio*
113 *rerio*) [19, 36, 37]. In the present study, we hypothesized that bath exposure to FA also affects the
114 mucosal immunity of the skin in rainbow trout. Additionally, we postulate that the direct effect
115 on mucosal immunity impacts bacterial growth rather than the FA itself affecting the bacteria.
116 The results of this study provide first insights into the benefits and risks of increasing DOC
117 concentrations in natural water bodies and aquaculture systems.

118 4 Experimental

119 4.1 Humic substance and experimental setup

120 The FA used in this study was obtained from HuminTech GmbH (Grevenbroich, Germany). The FA
121 contains 97 g C/L and is characterized by a high aromatic, especially phenolic content (for further
122 information, see Lieke et al. [36]). Fingerling rainbow trout were acquired from Uckermark-Fisch
123 GmbH (Boitzenburg, Germany). A total of 156 fish, weighing between 7.1 g and 17.6 g (with a
124 mean weight of 13.4 ± 2.6 g), were randomly distributed into six tanks (36 L, 26 fish per tank) of
125 three independent recirculating systems (415 L in total). Following acclimatization for two weeks,
126 the fish were exposed to different concentrations of FA (0, 5, and 50 mg C/L) for four weeks. The
127 fish were fed commercial food (Aller Silver, Aller Aqua, Germany), and 1.5 % of their weight was
128 given in two doses daily. Feeding was adjusted weekly to the predicted weight gain with an
129 assumed feed conversion ratio of 1. Temperature (16.5 ± 0.2 °C), pH (7.6 ± 0.1), and dissolved
130 oxygen (8.5 ± 0.5 mg/L) were monitored daily. Three times per week, nitrite (0.3 ± 0.3 mg/L),
131 nitrate (10.4 ± 2.0 mg/L), and ammonium (< 0.015 mg/L) were measured using the corresponding
132 kits (LCK304, LCK341, and LCK339, Hach Lange GmbH, Germany) and a photospectrometer
133 DR3900 (Hach Lange GmbH, Germany). Figure 1 shows the study design and hypotheses.

134
 135 *Figure 1: Study Design. Juvenile rainbow trout (Oncorhynchus mykiss) were exposed in a recirculating aquaculture system (RAS)*
 136 *for four weeks to different concentrations of the fulvic acid (0 mg C/L, 5 mg C/L, and 50 mg C/L). Following exposure, mucus from*
 137 *the skin was collected and analyzed photometrically for several mucosal immune parameters. Additionally, the number of colony-*
 138 *forming units of Yersinia ruckeri was determined with and without the mucus samples to analyze the antibacterial potential.*

139 **4.2 Mucus collection**

140 After four weeks, mucus was collected from five randomly selected fish per tank (n=10 per group)
 141 following Ross et al. [34]. Individual fish were transferred into a polyethylene bag containing 10
 142 mL of 50 mM NaCl and massaged gently by hand for two min to stimulate mucus production. The
 143 mucus was transferred to a 15 mL sterile centrifuge tube, centrifuged (1500 x g, 10 min, 4 °C) to
 144 remove epidermis cells and scales, and the supernatant was aliquoted and stored at -80 °C until
 145 subsequent analysis.

146 **4.3 Protein content**

147 Total protein content was quantified according to Bradford [38] by mixing 60 µL of mucus with
 148 140 µL of Bradford Reagent (Thermo Fischer Scientific, USA), followed by determining the
 149 absorbance at 595 nm using a microplate reader (Infinite 200, Tecan, Switzerland) after 5 min of
 150 incubation at room temperature. The albumin concentration was measured after precipitating
 151 immunoglobulin with 12 % PEG (polyethylene glycol, Merck, Germany, [39]). The concentration
 152 of immunoglobulin content was calculated as the difference between the total protein and
 153 albumin concentration.

154 4.4 Lysozyme Activity

155 Lysozyme activity was measured by using lyophilized *Micrococcus luteus* (*M. lysodeikticus* ATCC
156 No. 4698 (Sigma-Aldrich, USA)) (0.3 mg/mL in 0.025 M phosphate buffer, pH 6.2) as a substrate
157 [40]. The reduction in absorbance at 530 nm was measured in 1 min intervals for 15 min at 30 °C
158 using the Tecan Infinite 200. One unit of lysozyme activity was defined as the amount of enzyme
159 causing a decrease in absorbance of 0.001/min. The total protein content was used for
160 normalization.

161 4.5 Alkaline Phosphatase

162 Alkaline phosphatase activity was determined according to the method described by Ross et al.
163 [34]. In short, mucus samples were incubated at 30 °C with 4 mM para-nitrophenyl phosphate
164 (Genaxxon, Germany) in a 0.1 M ammonium bicarbonate buffer containing 1 mM MgCl₂ at pH
165 7.8. The para-nitrophenyl phosphate was enzymatically cleaved to produce para-nitrophenol, and
166 the absorbance was recorded using a microplate reader at 405 nm at 1 minute intervals for 3
167 hours. The linear rate was used to calculate the activity. A unit of activity was defined as the
168 increase in absorbance of 0.0001/min. The samples were normalized using total protein content.

169 4.6 Antibacterial Activity

170 *Yersinia ruckeri* was originally isolated from infected rainbow trout and cultivated on CASO agar
171 (Roth, Germany) at the Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries (Berlin,
172 Germany) for several years. Freshly grown colonies (less than one week old) were transferred into
173 CASO bouillon (Roth, Germany) and incubated at 20 °C (Mettler, Germany) for 48 h. Following
174 that, bacteria were inoculated with either mucus samples or sterile water and plated on CASO
175 agar (50 µL bacteria + 50 µL mucus or water). The samples were incubated at 20 °C for 48 h, and
176 the number of colony-forming units (CFU) was determined. Additionally, mucus was mixed with
177 sterile water to determine the bacterial background load. For each sample, three different
178 bacteria dilutions (10⁻⁵, 10⁻⁶, and 10⁻⁷) were used, with three replicates per mucus sample and
179 dilution. The experiment was repeated three times per mucus sample. Plates containing bacterial
180 numbers that were too low (< 10) or too high (>200) were excluded from the analysis. The number
181 of CFU from each background sample was subtracted from the mucus samples. The same

182 methodology was used to analyze the antibacterial capacity of FA (mixing FA directly with
183 bacteria).

184 4.7 Statistical analysis

185 The data was analyzed using RStudio 1.1.453 software. Normal distribution and variance
186 homogeneity were examined using the Shapiro-Wilk and Levene's tests, respectively. The
187 differences between the means of the treatment groups were analyzed with one-way ANOVA
188 followed by TukeyHSD posthoc testing under parametric conditions. If non-parametric testing
189 was required, the Kruskal-Wallis test was used with subsequent Dunn posthoc testing. Statistically
190 significant differences were identified at the $p < 0.05$ level. The figures show Tukey boxplots, with
191 outliers represented as dots or bar plots with mean and standard deviation.

192 5 Results

193 The present study evaluated the effects of FA bath exposure on selected mucosal immune
194 parameters of juvenile rainbow trout and its antibacterial activity against *Y. ruckeri*.

195 The total protein concentration of mucus samples was not affected by any of the FA
196 concentrations and was between 3.4 ± 0.7 mg/mL and 4.5 ± 1.2 mg/mL in all groups. In contrast,
197 the immunoglobulin concentration increased significantly following exposure to 50 mg C/L
198 compared to both the control group ($p=0.001$) and the 5 mg C/L group ($p=0.001$). Mucus samples
199 from control fish had an immunoglobulin concentration of 1.0 ± 0.4 mg/mL. However, in fish
200 exposed to 50 mg C/L, this concentration increased to 1.8 ± 0.3 mg/mL. There was no significant
201 difference in immunoglobulin concentration between fish exposed to 5 mg C/L and those in the
202 control group (1.1 ± 0.3 mg/mL). Although the albumin concentration was not affected by
203 exposure to any FA concentration, there was a notable shift in protein composition in the 50 mg
204 C/L group compared to the control ($p=0.038$) and low exposure group ($p=0.015$). While the mucus
205 from control fish was made up of 70.4 ± 7.3 % albumin and 29.6 ± 7.3 % immunoglobulin, fish
206 from the high exposure group had 57.7 ± 9.7 % albumin and 42.3 ± 9.7 % immunoglobulin. Fish
207 from the low FA exposure group had an albumin content of 73.0 ± 14.9 % and an immunoglobulin
208 content of 27.0 ± 14.9 %.

210

211 *Figure 2: Concentration (A) and composition (B) of mucus proteins after four weeks of exposure to fulvic acid. Small bold letters*
 212 *indicate significant differences in the total protein concentration; Large italic letters indicate significant differences in the albumin*
 213 *concentration and composition; Small italic letters indicate significant differences in the immunoglobulin concentration and*
 214 *composition.*

215 5.1 Enzymatic antibacterial activity of mucus

216 Exposure of rainbow trout to both FA concentrations significantly increased lysozyme (Fig. 3 A)
 217 and alkaline phosphatase (Fig. 3 B) activity in the mucus. Mucus from the control fish had an
 218 alkaline phosphatase activity of 1.6 ± 0.6 U/mg protein and a lysozyme activity of 2.0 ± 0.5 U/mg
 219 protein. In both exposure groups, lysozyme activity increased significantly to 4.1 ± 1.5 U/mg
 220 protein (5 mg C/L, $p < 0.001$) and 3.9 ± 1.2 U/mg protein (50 mg C/L, $p < 0.001$) compared to the
 221 control group. No significant difference was determined in mucus lysozyme activity between the
 222 two FA concentrations ($p = 0.76$). Similarly, alkaline phosphatase activity increased significantly in
 223 FA-exposed fish compared to unexposed fish. Interestingly, the low exposure group displayed the
 224 highest activity with 5.1 ± 1.3 U/mg protein ($p < 0.001$), while the activity in the 50 mg C/L group
 225 was 3.9 ± 0.7 U/mg protein ($p = 0.02$). Again, no significant difference was observed between the
 226 two exposure concentrations ($p = 0.17$).

227
 228 *Figure 3: Activity of lysozyme (A) and alkaline phosphatase (ALP, B) of skin mucus from rainbow trout (Oncorhynchus mykiss)*
 229 *exposed to fulvic acid for four weeks. Different letters indicate statistical differences between the groups.*

230 **5.2 Antibacterial capacity**

231 To determine if activation of defense mechanisms can reduce bacterial load on fish, mucus
 232 samples were inoculated with *Y. ruckeri*, and the number of colony-forming units (CFUs) was
 233 measured.

234 The addition of mucus from control fish significantly reduced the number of growing bacteria
 235 from $384.0 \pm 63.7 \times 10^6$ cells/mL to $170 \pm 67.2 \times 10^6$ cells/mL, reflecting a reduction of 55.5 %
 236 ($p=0.001$). The addition of both concentrations of FA to the water further reduced the bacterial
 237 load to 26.3 % and 26.5 %, respectively ($101.2 \pm 55.1 \times 10^6$ cells/mL in the low FA group and 101.6
 238 $\pm 46.9 \times 10^6$ cells/mL in the high FA group). While the reduction in bacterial growth was highly
 239 significant in both FA exposure groups compared to the control mucus ($p<0.001$) and unrestricted
 240 growth ($p<0.001$), there was no difference between the two FA concentrations ($p=0.81$). The
 241 bacterial load of the pure mucus ranged from 53.9 ± 40.3 to 124.0 ± 174.6 CFU/mL (data not
 242 shown) and showed no significant difference between the groups ($p=0.48$ for 50 mg C/L against
 243 both other groups and $p=0.96$ for 5 mg C/L against the control). Neither 5 mg C/L nor 50 mg C/L
 244 of FA affected the bacterial growth.

245

246 *Figure 4: Number of colony forming units (CFU) of Yersinia ruckeri after 48 h incubation with sterile water or mucus from fish with*
 247 *and without fulvic acid to the water.*

248 6 Discussion

249 Skin mucosal immunity undeniably plays a crucial role in protecting fish against the invasion of
 250 pathogenic microorganisms as a first line of defense [41]. However, the complete mechanisms
 251 are not yet fully understood [42]. Under artificial conditions, such as high stocking densities in
 252 aquaculture, pathogen loads can easily exceed those found under unpolluted natural conditions.
 253 However, it is important to note that industrial waste and livestock effluent can contribute to high
 254 pathogen loads in adjacent natural waters [43, 44]. In case of high exposure to pathogens, the
 255 natural defense mechanisms of fish are often insufficient to combat pathogens, resulting in
 256 diseases and high mortality [45]. Therefore, strengthening the natural defense mechanisms is a
 257 desirable approach to protect fish in aquaculture from diseases and reduce the need for chemical
 258 therapeutics and antibiotics [46, 47]. Determining the effects of FA on fish mucosal immunity will
 259 also help to assess the potential hazards associated with increasing concentrations of DOC in
 260 natural water sources.

261 In the present study, exposure of juvenile rainbow trout to FA for four weeks significantly
 262 increased several skin mucosal immune parameters and decreased the growth of *Y. ruckeri*.
 263 Lysozyme and alkaline phosphatase are essential enzymes that contribute to the natural
 264 resistance of fish to pathogens. Fish lysozyme was identified in rainbow trout in 1988 [48] and

265 catalyzes the cleavage of the β 1-4 linkage between N-acetylmuramic acid and N-
266 acetylglucosamine of the peptidoglycan layer, inducing lysis of bacteria [49, 50]. Lysozyme plays
267 an important role in aquatic animals, and the effective killing of both Gram⁺ and Gram⁻ bacteria
268 has been reported for fish lysozyme [51-53]. Notably, the antibacterial effect against Gram⁻
269 bacteria requires additional mechanisms to hydrolyze the β 1-4 bonds, including synergistic
270 effects with other innate immune components, electrostatic interactions, and activation of
271 bacterial autolysis [54-56]. Upon infection with parasites and pathogens, lysozyme activity is
272 induced, demonstrating the importance of these defense mechanisms against actual diseases [57,
273 58].

274 Exposure to 5 and 50 mg C/L of the FA significantly increased the lysozyme activity by 2-fold
275 compared to unexposed fish. However, there was no difference between the two exposure
276 groups. This result differs slightly from our previous results, where the lysozyme activity in the
277 gills was increased only after exposure to 50 mg C/L of the same FA [36]. Lysozyme is mainly
278 produced by macrophages [56]. Our previous study indicated an increase in myeloid cells
279 following exposure of zebrafish larvae to FA [19]. An increased number of macrophages and other
280 lysozyme-producing cells by FA could explain the increased activity found in the mucus. In
281 addition, the degradation of bacteria by lysozyme releases pathogen-associated molecular
282 patterns (PAMPs), which recruit more phagocytes, creating a positive feedback loop.

283 Similar to lysozyme activity, the alkaline phosphatase activity increased in the mucus following FA
284 exposure. Again, there was no significant difference between the exposure groups; however,
285 there was a trend toward lower activity in the 50 mg C/L group (a 2.5-fold increase compared to
286 a 3.2-fold increase in the 5 mg C/L group). Alkaline phosphatase catalyzes the hydrolysis of organic
287 phosphate esters, such as lipopolysaccharides (LPS), flagellins, and DNA CpG motifs [32].
288 Increased alkaline phosphatase activity has been reported following bacterial and parasitic
289 infections related to wounding [34, 35]. Additionally, environmental stress activates the alkaline
290 phosphatase [32, 59]. Due to its phenolic character, FA contains a high amount of persistent free
291 radicals [60], which can induce oxidative stress. Although no significant adverse effects were
292 observed at 50 mg C/L, FA induced the transcription of genes involved in antioxidative defense,
293 including superoxide dismutase-2 and the nrf2-keap1 pathway [19]. This oxidative stress may

294 explain the observed activation of alkaline phosphatase after exposure. The exact mechanisms
295 causing this activation have not yet been elucidated. Dephosphorylation of pathogenic
296 compounds attenuates the pro-inflammatory response, and alkaline phosphatase is thought to
297 play an essential role in wound healing [61, 62]. Stimulating the alkaline phosphatase can protect
298 fish from pathogens and accelerate wound healing. However, activating the immune response
299 and coping with stress can be highly energy demanding, and may reduce feed intake and
300 conversion, reproduction, and even lifespan [63-65].

301 Natural organic matter, including FA, can interact with proteins through adsorption,
302 copolymerization, or encapsulation within the internal structure of the organic matter or
303 electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions [66-69]. The resulting conformational change can
304 partially inactivate the enzyme. In reverse, the interaction can also increase the stability of the
305 protein or lead to an increased affinity of the enzyme for substrates and cofactors, increasing the
306 overall increase in activity [70, 71]. Such stabilization may result in the accumulation of lysozyme
307 and alkaline phosphatase within the mucus of fish exposed to FA, explaining the increased activity
308 found in the present study.

309 The environment shapes biological processes in complex ways. The aryl hydrocarbon receptor
310 (AHR) is a vital component that detects and integrates environmental signals, including
311 xenobiotics and variations in oxygen tension and redox potentials [72, 73]. Most immune cells,
312 including antigen-presenting cells (APCs) such as dendritic cells and macrophages, express the
313 AHR [72, 74, 75], and AHR signaling regulates their differentiation and functions, such as cytokine
314 expression. Upon ligand activation or altered redox potentials, AHR translocates into the nucleus
315 and activates gene transcription in the xenobiotic response element (XRE) [72]. AHR also
316 regulates multiple aspects of the immune response through XRE-dependent and independent
317 pathways [76-78]. Humic substances activate the AHR pathway, as reported by Bittner et al.
318 (2006) [79] and Janošek et al. (2007) [80]. One possible explanation for the observed increases in
319 immune parameters in this study is the activation of the AHR pathway by FA.

320 AHR also strongly interacts with the NF- κ B (Nuclear factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of
321 activated B cells) and MAPK (Mitogen-activated protein kinases) pathways in regulating the
322 function of innate immune cells and the production of immunomodulatory cytokines [81-84]. FA

323 is structurally comparable to many phytogetic compounds (high aromatic, especially phenolic
324 content), and these have also been shown to affect the skin mucosal immune response and
325 antibacterial activity in fish [85-87]. Thymol and carvacrol, for example, also interfere with the
326 NF-kB and MAPK pathways, modulating the expression of inflammatory cytokines and several
327 inflammatory processes [88, 89]. Firmino et al. [90] suggested that bioactive compounds in
328 phytoGENICS activate transient receptor potential (TRP) cation channels, which increases
329 intracellular Ca^{2+} concentration and activates MAPK/NF-kB signaling pathways. A similar
330 mechanism is possible for FA. Nevertheless, additional studies are needed to clarify whether the
331 AHR pathway and subsequent NF-kB and MAPK activation are the primary mechanisms through
332 which FA stimulates the mucosal immune response.

333 Reactive oxygen species (ROS) not only cause oxidative damage and play an important role during
334 phagocytosis but are also key components in several immune pathways [91, 92]. Extracellular ROS
335 acts as a chemoattractant for monocytes and promotes differentiation into macrophages [93, 94].
336 Furthermore, ROS induce the NF-kB pathway by degrading the inhibitory subunit of NF-kB (I kappa
337 B) [95], leading to the expression of a large number of pro-inflammatory cytokines and
338 inflammatory mediators such as tumor necrosis factor (TNF-a), interleukin-1 (IL-1) and
339 interleukin-6 (IL-6). These recruit and activate several immune cells, and increased numbers and
340 activation of neutrophils and macrophages in the skin mucus could explain the increase in
341 lysozyme and overall antibacterial capacity after FA exposure [96, 97].

342 Immunoglobulins (Igs) are the main humoral component of innate and adaptive immune
343 responses, playing a central role in protecting against infectious diseases [98]. Secreted Igs (sIgs)
344 recognize and coat infectious agents, aiding in their destruction by phagocytes or the complement
345 system [99]. Nevertheless, sIgs also coat beneficial microbiota [100-102]. The coating of beneficial
346 bacteria may play a critical role in colonizing and positioning bacteria within the outer mucus
347 layer, promoting homeostasis [103]. The skin mucus in fish contains mostly IgT (also known as
348 IgZ), which performs similar functions to mammalian IgA and is the prevalent Ig isotype in mucus
349 [101, 104, 105]. It is essential for removing mucosal pathogens and maintaining the balance of
350 microbiota [90]. Exposure to 50 mg C/L FA significantly increased the concentration and content
351 of Ig in the mucus compared to the control fish. In contrast, 5 mg C/L had no effect. An increase

352 in the amount of slgs, as observed in the present study, may aid fish in responding more
353 effectively to invading microorganisms. The fast recognition and coating of pathogens could
354 effectively trap them in the mucus and mark them for rapid degradation. However, the increased
355 concentration of slgs and the altered Ig : albumin ratio will likely also impact both beneficial and
356 commensal bacteria, with unknown effects on the microbiome. Increased expression levels of
357 mucosal Ig have been observed following bath vaccination and are thought to contribute to
358 protection against infections [106, 107]. Rainbow trout infected with *Ichthyophthirius multifiliis*
359 had significantly higher numbers of IgT⁺ B cells and higher concentrations of IgT in the skin mucus
360 compared to control fish [105, 108]. Fish experimentally depleted of mucosal IgT were highly
361 susceptible to *I. multifiliis* infection [109], demonstrating the crucial role of this immune
362 component in protection. Since proteases can trigger Igs production, the increased activity of
363 alkaline proteases in the present study, may explain the elevated levels of Igs in the mucus [110].
364 Then again, an increase in the number or activity of B cells producing immunoglobulins, mediated
365 through AHR/NF-κB/MAPK, could result in a higher amount of Igs secreted into the mucus.

366 6.1 Antibacterial activity of skin mucus

367 *In vitro* inoculating *Y. ruckeri* with mucus collected from control fish skin decreased the CFU to
368 56 %, demonstrating the high antimicrobial potency of fish mucus itself. Antibacterial activity was
369 further increased by exposure to both FA concentrations, resulting in a 74 % decrease in CFU. HSS
370 can directly impact bacterial and fungal growth, both inhibiting and promoting it, depending on
371 the chemical characteristics of the HS [111-113]. However, the FA used in this study did not
372 directly affect *the growth of Y. ruckeri*. Thus, the growth inhibition found is mediated by the
373 increased immune response of the fish rather than by direct antibacterial activities of FA. Our
374 previous study showed increased defense mechanisms in the gills of rainbow trout, especially
375 after being exposed to 50 mg C/L [36]. The skin mucus appears more sensitive to FA exposure,
376 leading to increased defense activity even after exposure to 5 mg C/L of FA. Noteworthy, while 5
377 mg C/L increased mainly the innate immune parameter, 50 mg C/L also increased the Ig
378 concentration, indicating a possible involvement of the adaptive immune response at this
379 concentration.

380 In addition to the activation of lysozyme and alkaline phosphatase and the increased Ig
381 concentration in mucus, changes in the microbiota could also contribute to the increased
382 antibacterial activity. The microbiota is an important part of the mucosal barrier and strongly
383 influences fish health and disease control through complex host-microbiota interactions. Several
384 beneficial bacteria in fish skin mucus are antagonistic to known fish pathogens. For example,
385 members of the *Roseobacter* clade produce metabolites (e.g., tropodithetic acid - TDA) with
386 antibacterial activity against *Vibrio anguillarum* [114]. A molecule from *Bacillus subtilis* showed
387 strong antimicrobial activity against 13 different pathogenic bacteria strains, including methicillin
388 and vancomycin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* [115]. Beneficial microbes can also inhibit the
389 *quorum-sensing* ability of pathogens [116].

390 Furthermore, Hu et al. [117] demonstrated that a shift in the mucus of male zebrafish after
391 combined oral exposure to perfluorobutanesulfonate and *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* was
392 accompanied by increases in lysozyme activity, Ig concentration, and peroxidase activity.
393 Furthermore, the relative abundances of *Hyphomicrobium* and *Limnobacter* bacteria correlated
394 with the activity of ALP. Louvado et al. [17] reported that exposure to a HSs modulated the fish
395 bacterial community in European sea bass, with increased relative abundance of the *Roseobacter*
396 clade. An alteration in the skin microbiome by FA could also cause the increased antibacterial
397 activity demonstrated in the presented study.

398 7 Conclusion

399 HSs, including FA, are naturally occurring, omnipresent organic substances. They are gaining
400 increasing attention for their beneficial potential as agricultural supplements and increasing
401 concentrations in natural waters. Evaluating their benefits and potentially toxic effects is of great
402 importance. To the best of our knowledge, our study is the first to show the modulatory effects
403 of HSs on the skin mucosal immune response of fish. The results indicate that a 5 mg C/L and 50
404 mg C/L FA bath exposure increases several aspects of skin mucosal immunity, consequently
405 increasing the antibacterial activity of the mucus. Rising concentrations in natural water from
406 climate change and anthropogenic influences might also enhance the resistance of fish against
407 microorganisms in the beginning. However, the broad effect on the immune system raises

408 concerns about its impact on the beneficial resident bacteria in the skin mucous. The extent of
409 these effects and their potential risks on the microbiota are not yet fully understood. As these
410 symbiotic microorganisms play a crucial role in maintaining health, further research is needed to
411 identify the complex interplay between the immunomodulatory effects of FA and the balance of
412 the skin microbiota.

413 Although the immune-stimulating effects of FA show promise for short-term application in
414 intensely monitored systems, such as aquaculture, long-term exposure to increasing
415 concentrations, as occurring in nature, may pose overlooked risks.

416 8 Data availability

417 All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published article.

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424 10 Authors Contribution

425 **T. Lieke:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – Original Draft,
426 Writing – Review & Editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding
427 acquisition; **S. Behrens:** Methodology, Investigation; **C. E. W. Steinberg:** Writing – Review &
428 Editing; **T. Meinelt:** Funding acquisition

429 11 Ethical statement

430 Experiments were conducted according to principles published in the European animal directive
431 (2010/63/EU) and the national laws (Act No 246/1992 “Animal welfare”, on the protection of
432 animals against cruelty) for the protection of animals used in scientific experiments. Animal
433 experiments have been approved by the Ministry of Agriculture. Experimental fish were

434 maintained and controlled by specially trained personnel according to FELASA B and §17
435 paragraph 1 of act 246/1992 and in accordance with requirements of act 246/1992 of Czech Code
436 of Law.

437 12 Competing Interests

438 The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest. The founding sponsor had no role in
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